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IL23R expression in the blood marks onset of disease severity in Crohn's Disease.

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IL23R functional variants are protective against (confer protection from) development of inflammatory bowel disease. We report here that activation (differential expression rather than genetic variation) of IL23R was associated with onset of disease severity in humans with Crohn's Disease. Interleukin-23 is specifically associated with risk for development of IBD as well as disease activity or severity in humans with IBD.